

EXCELERATE Deliverable 8.3

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1. Executive Summary

In this report we describe the past and planned future workshops for the rare disease (RD) domain within the context of the ELIXIR-EXCELERATE project with the aims (1) to identify key training contacts/subjects in the RD community, (2) to identify specific training needs in the RD community and (3) to spread specific knowledge needed in the RD community. An important mission of EXCELERATE WP8 'ELIXIR infrastructure for Rare Disease research', defined at the kick-off meeting on November 24, 2015 in Leiden, is to help the rare disease community in different nodes to raise its infrastructure activities to the level of best practices in ELIXIR infrastructure, i.e. where rare disease data, metadata, tools, and catalogues are shared, interoperable, and sustainable at the source, conform a common set of principles and standards across participating countries/nodes and in agreement with the ELIXIR platforms. To achieve optimal knowledge exchange between the domains, workshops in this WP are typically co-organised with members from the rare disease community and co-sponsored by relevant projects such as RD-Connect .

Events were either organised specifically with the Rare Disease (RD) community, or a separate stream/session for the RD community was co-organised around other events. Training workshops and courses were delivered in partnership with WP11 'EXCELERATE Training Programme'.

The delivery of workshops was complemented by the ELIXIR implementation study/RD-Connect proof-of-concept to test interoperability backbone components for enabling queries across rare disease biobanks and registries.

2. Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	Build the ELIXIR registry of data resources and analysis tools critical for the development of the rare disease research. (Task 8.1)		x
2	Continuous monitoring of resources and tools in Rare-diseases.		x
3	Implementation of a system for the generation of datasets adequate for the assessment of methods in the area of rare-diseases.		x
4	Implementation of the ELIXIR rare-disease portfolio in the ELIXIR registry.		x
5	Implementation of a technical framework for the comparison and standardization of services useful for the rare-disease communities. (Task 8.2)		x
6	Collaboration with the rare-disease communities for the organization of training courses, workshops and jamborees. (Task 8.3)	x	

3. Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: Yes No

4. Adjustments made

No adjustments were made.

5. Background information

Background information on this WP as originally indicated in the description of action (DoA) is included here for reference.

Work package number	8	Start date or starting event:	month 1
Work package title	Use Case C: ELIXIR infrastructure for Rare Disease research		
Lead	Ivo Gut (ES) and Marco Roos (NL)		
Participant number and person months per participant			
4 – UNIMAN 6.00, 6 – NBIC 0.00, LUMC 6.00, 7 – CNIO 10.00, 8 – CRG 38.40, 10 – IRB 12.00, 12 – BSC 10.00, 22 – NTNU 12.00, 26 – CNRS 12.00, 30 – CNR 3.00, 32 – UL 15.00, 38 – DTU 12.00			

The International Rare Diseases Research Consortium (<http://www.irdirc.org>) established the ambitious goal of developing 200 new therapies by 2020. ELIXIR as a whole and in particular this Work Package is aligned with this effort. The overall objective of this Work Package (WP) is to address the needs of the rare diseases community through the instantiation of the ELIXIR resources described in WP1-5. These resources do not constitute a replacement of the current research projects organized around the rare diseases area. Indeed the aim is to empower them and to help in the sustainability of the resources created by these projects in the long term.

Work Package Lead: Ivo Gut (ES) and Marco Roos (NL)

Objectives

WP8 aims to empower actors involved in the development of new rare diseases therapies through the execution of the following specific objectives:

- Build the ELIXIR registry of data resources and analysis tools critical for the development of the rare disease research. (Task 8.1)
- Continuous monitoring of resources and tools in Rare-diseases.
- Implementation of a system for the generation of datasets adequate for the assessment of methods in the area of rare- diseases.
- Implementation of the ELIXIR rare-disease portfolio in the ELIXIR registry.
- Implementation of a technical framework for the comparison and standardization of services useful for the rare-disease communities. (Task 8.2)
- Collaboration with the rare-disease communities for the organization of training courses, workshops and jamborees. (Task 8.3)

Description of work and role of partners

This WP is organised around the actors that play a major role on the development of these new therapies. These actors are the main users of the ELIXIR infrastructure: data generators and curators (usually personnel working in hospitals, genomics-based companies, and members of large research consortia), researchers (bioinformaticians, geneticists, and clinical doctors), diagnosis companies, CROs (usually SMEs), and the pharmaceutical industry among others

Task 8.1: The ELIXIR portfolio of data resources developed in collaboration with the rare diseases communities. (69.4PM)

Subtask 8.1.1 Monitoring of resources and tools. (25.4PM)

There is a wide range of data resources and analysis methods used in the rare-disease area. Many of those resources are provided by ELIXIR Nodes, for example the European Genome-Phenome archive (EGA) currently stores data from major research initiatives in rare diseases like the RD-connect project. In this subtask we will review the current data resources and evaluate their usability and potential impact on the rare disease community. An important aspect of the evaluation will be the security of the data that is a key aspect in rare disease domain given the low frequency of the associated genomic variants in the population.

One critical aspect of the development of the registry is to engage the different communities in the submission and rating of the tools. In this task we will work together with representatives of the major projects in the field of rare- diseases to create a customized portfolio of ELIXIR tools and services devoted to assist them in the development of these new therapies. As an example we will ask for proposals of tools that serve to interpret the effect of genomics variants on a group of patients that belong to the same family. We strongly believe that this link between the end- users and the

tools developers will help ELIXIR to understand better the problems that are actually facing the main actors in the rare diseases research and hence to better solutions.

The final outcome of this task will be the ELIXIR data resources and analysis tools useful to the rare disease communities.

Partners: NO, ES, SI, IT, NL

Subtask 8.1.2: Creation of reference datasets adequate for the specific assessment of methods and standards in the area of rare-diseases. (30PM)

While the creation of these tools should stay as a priority for researchers, large scale projects, SMEs and the industry increasingly need access to benchmarked methods on which to build their analysis strategies.

The evaluation of the methods requires the adequate selection of the datasets and benchmarking strategies. The systems for the selection of the datasets for the benchmarking have to be fast and effective to enable the continuous evaluation of the methods, as described in WP2. We will collaborate with the ELIXIR benchmarking strategy (WP2) to build the appropriate strategies for the selection of the datasets (subtask 8.1.1 above) and with the rare- disease communities to implement the adequate quality reporting standards. Moreover we will integrate these pipelines in the ELIXIR benchmarking framework (WP2) to continuously monitor the selected methods with the newly generated datasets. Partners: ES, DK, IT,FR, SI, UK

Subtask 8.1.3 Implementation of the ELIXIR rare-disease portfolio in the ELIXIR registry. (14PM)

The ELIXIR registry will be a reference for the research community (WP1), as it will reflect the quality and the real- time status of the services included on it. This registry will act as a one-stop shop for services provided by ELIXIR. The goal is to allow users from the different countries, communities and projects to discover which are the tools available at a given time, with the associated information about the community based rating (see WP2), instructions for correct use and associated examples We will encourage tools developers to adopt the EDAM standard to describe their tools and to share several metrics about the performance and usage of these of the tools (see description in WP1)

Those services promoted as relevant by the end-users will be listed in a special section in the ELIXIR registry. Partners: DK, ES, FR.

Task 8.2: Standardisation of rare disease services in collaboration with the RD communities. (36PM)

The ecosystem of RD services will inevitably be a combination of distributed and centralized resources, because of the sheer number of rare diseases and rare disease organisations, as well as legal and ethical constraints between countries and communities. At the same time, because of the low frequency in the population, combining data across patient registries, biobanks, and -omics databases is the single most important way of getting new insights towards new treatments.

One of the most recurrent issues when attempting to perform research across resources is the lack of standards or the poor adoption of existing standards by RD stakeholders. Rare disease standards concern different types of data including genomic and phenotypic characteristics, causative genetic variation status, quality criteria, analysis protocols, supporting evidence and follow-up indicators. These problems will be analysed in workshops including experts in semantic web, linked data technologies and rare-disease experts (see previous experiences and proposal in “Bring Your Own Data (BYOD) bootcamps”, in WP5). The initial experience with this methodology (see 61) is that a critical bottleneck is the identification of the most appropriate terms and identifiers to annotate data for cross- resource questions. Based on this experience we aim to

address two major 'white spots' in the available infrastructure for Rare-diseases: (i) the current infrastructure of the rare disease platform: RD-Connect, does not contain backbone services for functional interlinking, (ii) a majority of RD sources are not equipped to provide data, metadata, and data updates using appropriate standard procedures. To address these needs we will work together with WP5, the rare-disease communities and the RD-Connect project to (i) deploy and test the services and guidelines for standardization 'at the source', (ii) provide standardized interfaces that Rare-disease communities can work with from a central location, (iii) build capacity in the RD community by enabling them to work with these services themselves.

Partners: FR, ES, DK, NL.

Task 8.3: Training workshops targeting different user communities. (32PM)

In this task training workshops and courses will be delivered, in partnership with WP11 "EXCELERATE Training Programme". The training will be approached from two sides. First, in collaboration with the Train the Researcher task in WP11 we will train rare diseases' researchers in the use of relevant tools, standards and infrastructure produced by ELIXIR. Second, we will run "feedback workshops" in which those who are developing the methods will be exposed directly to problems faced by the rare disease community. These userthons will help to shape the ELIXIR portfolio. The direct collaboration with WP11 Train the Researcher will ensure that researchers are trained to a high standard in state-of-the-art analysis techniques for rare disease data and that innovative training approaches developed in this task are applied elsewhere in ELIXIR.

Partners: UK, SI, NL

6. Annex 1: REPORT: ELIXIR workshops organized with the Rare Disease community

REPORT: ELIXIR workshops organized with the Rare Disease community

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Summary

In this report we describe the past and planned future workshops for the rare disease (RD) domain within the context of the ELIXIR-EXCELERATE project with the aims (1) to identify key training contacts/subjects in the RD community, (2) to identify specific training needs in the RD community and (3) to spread specific knowledge needed in the RD community. An important mission of EXCELERATE WP8 'ELIXIR infrastructure for Rare Disease research', defined at the kick-off meeting on November 24, 2015 in Leiden, is to help the rare disease community in different nodes to raise its infrastructure activities to the level of best practices in ELIXIR infrastructure, i.e. where rare disease data, metadata, tools, and catalogues are shared, interoperable, and sustainable at the source, conform a common set of principles and standards across participating countries/nodes and in agreement with the ELIXIR platforms. To achieve optimal knowledge exchange between the domains, workshops in this WP are typically co-organised with members from the

rare disease community and co-sponsored by relevant projects such as RD-Connect¹.

Events were either organised specifically with the Rare Disease (RD) community, or a separate stream/session for the RD community was co-organised around other events. Training workshops and courses were delivered in partnership with WP11 'EXCELERATE Training Programme'.

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¹ <http://rd-connect.eu/>

1. Workshops for and with the rare disease community

EXCELERATE members contribute to the workshops by advising in rare disease workshops, mediating them and organising the contribution of data experts, such as in the case of Bring Your Own Data events - BYODs (contributions of Marco Roos and Mascha Jansen for ELIXIR-NL). Based on the experience from the workshops, they take initiatives towards collaboratively developing protocols and tooling (e.g. the rare disease data linkage plan co-led by EXCELERATE WP8 co-lead Marco Roos), define new training goals (led by Brane Leskosek and Celia van Gelder for WP8/11), and further developing the Rare Disease Connect platform (led by WP8 co-leads Ivo Gut and Sergi Beltran). The objectives of the contributions are: (i) to stimulate and foster rare disease data resources to become FAIR at the source (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable for humans and computers), (ii) to stimulate the rare disease community to share (meta)data via the RD-Connect platform and European infrastructures such as EGA. Below is a description of five specific workshops organised within the RD domain (Table 1).

TABLE 1: LIST OF WORKSHOPS AND EVENTS

Nr.	Place	Date	Event	Participants	Participants	Topic
1	Rome, IT	24–25 Sep 2015	RD-Connect workshop data linkage and ontologies	NL, IT, UK, AT, EL, ES, DE, FR, RO	23	Hands-on tutorial for (aspiring) managers of rare disease registries.
2	Utrecht, NL	30 Nov–4 Dec 2015	Managing and Integrating Life Science Information	IT, NL, SI, UK, EBI	10	Managing large, heterogeneous (FAIR) data sources (including RD sources) with exploitation principles.
3	Barcelona, ES	8 Mar 2016	ELIXIR All-Hands	all ELIXIR members + AT	20+	ELIXIR and RD-Connect workshop.
4	Helsinki, FI	13-15 June 2016	Variant Analysis Workshop	FI, ES, FR, EBI, EE, DE	43	ELIXIR and RD-Connect workshop.
5	Rome, IT	27-29 Jul 2016	Next generation registries: going FAIR, going Gold	NL, IT, UK, AT, EL, ES, DE, FR, RO, USA	21 (+5 remote connection)	

1.1. Data linkage and ontologies

Collaborative workshop with RD-Connect

Rome, 24–25 September 2015

From 2014 onwards, BYODs and their follow-up have played an important role for the collaborative, cross-project endorsement of interoperable data infrastructure for the rare disease domain. ELIXIR members have contributed significantly to the success of these workshops. In this particular event, also coined ‘a BYOD for beginners’, stakeholders who manage a disease registry or were planning to create a new rare disease registry were introduced to an approach that prepares data for cross-resource analysis via uniform resource identifiers and ontologies. Via a simple tutorial they simulated enabling questions across federated multi-lingual registries. Participants created mock registries and from them a mock catalogue to answer basic questions. First, a traditional approach was used based on merging tables and then an approach was used based on using ontological concepts and Linked Data. It showed how problems caused by ambiguity of terms and language differences can be mitigated by using standardised, computer-readable identifiers that are linked to ontologies. The guided hands-on session was preceded by introductory lectures on data linkage basics (M. Roos; LUMC/ELIXIR-NL), application ontologies (S. Sarntivijai; EBI), and WikiData (A. Waagmeester; Micelio).

The event (<http://www.iss.it/cnmr/?lang=1&id=2585&tipo=3>) was held on the two days following an annual summer school organised by ISS². The meeting was organised in collaboration with the RD-Connect linked data and ontologies task force (<http://rd-connect.eu/platform/registries/linked-data-and-ontology-task-force/>), the Leiden University Medical Center (<http://www.lumc.nl>), ELIXIR (<https://www.elixir-europe.org/>), and ELIXIR-NL/DTL (<http://www.dtls.nl/>).

The event was following the aim of delivering specific knowledge to the RD community to raise capacity of the participants.

1.2. Managing and Integrating Life Science Information

Collaborative BioSB/RD-Connect/ELIXIR-NL Course

Utrecht, 30 November–4 December 2015

At the 4th edition of this course, which is part of the BioSB course portfolio (www.biosb.nl), new techniques for working with large, heterogeneous data sources were shown together with the principles on how to exploit existing information³. FAIR principles and methods for linking one's own data into a global distributed web of resources and using such a distributed web were introduced. In lectures and hands-on sessions participants were introduced to minimal information models, Linked Data (RDF), ontologies, API-centric systems, and choosing identifiers for data and metadata, and the use of computational workflows to analyse data. OpenPHACTS and FAIRdom were used as examples. The course contributed to the development of a plan to make rare disease registries and biobanks linkable *at the source* and the

² Istituto Superiore di Sanità (<http://www.iss.it/>, Rome, Italy)

³ <http://biosb.nl/education/course-portfolio/course-managing-and-integrating-information-in-the-life-sciences/>

inclusion of interoperability criteria for evaluating registries and biobanks. These were presented at the ELIXIR All-Hands meeting and RD-Connect annual meeting, March, 2016.

The event was following the aim of delivering specific knowledge to the RD community to raise capacity of the participants. Participants included researchers representing rare disease patient registries, Elixir-Slovenia, Elixir-NL, and bioinformatics researchers working in academia and industry. One of the two coordinators is the co-lead of RD WP8 (M. Roos), while one of the tutors is associated with Elixir-EBI (S. Jupp).

1.3. ELIXIR All-Hands Meeting

Barcelona, 8 March 2016

A common ELIXIR and RD-Connect workshop was organised as a special session at the ELIXIR All-Hands meeting in Barcelona. Agreement was reached for making the RD training needs survey in line with the WP11 training needs survey. Based on the survey results, new training courses and workshops will be prepared and offered to the RD community. The RD training needs survey will use the same core questions as the WP11 survey with possible extension for RD specifics. Key contacts for RD training needs were identified across RD community and it will be used for the RD training needs survey.

Furthermore, key topics for the rare disease community were identified for ELIXIR members. These were used as requirements for tools for the community, the RD-Connect platform, and the rare disease data linkage plan⁴. The topics included person identification, data identifiers and metadata formats, EGA data storage and EGA metadata and guidelines, data elements such as phenotypes and their descriptions, sequence-based variants and genetics information that is not sequence based, aggregation of patient, disease and biosample data and connecting registries with similar kinds of data.

Application ontologies were discussed, the need to identify overlap in ontologies and mapping between ontologies, recommendable ontologies such as ORDO, HPO, OMIM and SNOMED-CT, the difficulties of ontology use by clinicians, tools to go from human readable to machine readable terms (e.g. Zooma), and tools that make use of harmonized annotation such as look-up systems, match-making, beacons and FAIR data points.

Constraints of moving from local installations to international collaborations, sustainability, visibility, and scalability were discussed, as well as who from the RD community defines the requirements for infrastructure and tools, and how to address alignment with other infrastructures such as BBMRI. A survey for tools and resources will help to establish computing needs for benchmarking. For example benchmarking of negative cases is unresolved.

Possible implementation study suggestions were discussed, such as for finding registries that promote retrospective harmonization, and candidate use cases and driving questions (e.g. eligibility for a clinical trials).

The event was following the aims of identifying key training contacts and specific training needs in the RD community and delivered specific knowledge to the RD community to raise capacity of the participants.

⁴ <https://goo.gl/ujOamD>

1.4. Variant Analysis Workshop

Helsinki, 13–15 June 2016

This workshop, which is part of the ELIXIR Train-the-researcher workshop series, covered several aspects of variant analysis including annotation and prioritization. The course consisted of three independent days, which participants could combine according to their needs. Each course day contained both lectures and hands-on exercises, which were suitable for everybody as analysis was performed with easy-to-use graphical tools. This course was organized by the [ELIXIR EXCELERATE](#) project together with [RD-Connect](#). The website of the course is <https://www.csc.fi/web/training/-/variant-analysis> and most of the sessions were recorded on video and have been made available through youtube: <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLjiXAZO27eICDh3RrkpmnQLfLuyIqL2Bz>

The programme and summary of the sessions was:

Introduction to variant analysis from sequencing data (13 June 2016)

(Maria Lehtivaara and Eija Korpelainen (CSC))

This introductory day covered variant analysis from raw sequence reads to variant annotation, introducing the theory, analysis tools and file formats involved. The program consisted of alternating short lectures and hands-on exercises. As the user-friendly [Chipster](#) software was used in the exercises, no previous knowledge of Unix or R was required and the tutorial was thus suitable for everybody. The following topics and analysis tools were covered:

- quality control (FastQC, PRINSEQ)
- preprocessing (Trimmomatic)
- alignment (BWA)
- alignment level QC (Samtools)
- marking duplicates (Picard)
- calling and filtering variants (Samtools, BCFtools, VCFtools)
- variant annotation (VEP)
- visualizing variants in genomic context (Chipster genome browser using Ensembl data)

Variant annotation and effect prediction (14 June 2016)

Session 1: Protein structure analysis of mutations using HOPE (Hanka Venselaar, CMBI, Radboudumc)

[HOPE](#) is an automatic mutant analysis server that can provide insight into the structural effects of a mutation. It is aimed at users in the biomedical field who wish to visualize and understand their mutation of interest. Given a sequence and mutation, HOPE will show the effect of that mutation in such a way that also those without a bioinformatics background can understand it.

Session 2: Ensembl: Analysing variation data with the Variant Effect Predictor (Benjamin Moore, EBI)

The [Ensembl project](#) provides a comprehensive and integrated source of annotation of mainly vertebrate genome sequences. The session began with an introduction to the Ensembl project, gene model annotations and variation data followed by hands-on demonstrations and exercises focused on viewing the range of variation data available in Ensembl. We also explored how [BioMart](#) can be used as a flexible tool for accessing and downloading a variety of different types of variation data from Ensembl.

The second part of the session covered the [Variant Effect Predictor \(VEP\)](#) in detail and how this tool can be used to analyse variation data. VEP determines the effect of variants (SNPs, insertions, deletions, CNVs or structural variants) on genes, transcripts, and protein sequence, as well as regulatory regions. Given the coordinates and nucleotide changes, it reports the genes and transcripts affected and the location of the variants (e.g. upstream of a transcript, in coding sequence, in non-coding RNA, in regulatory regions). It also reports for example the consequence of the variants on the protein sequence (e.g. stop gained, missense, stop lost, frameshift) and SIFT and PolyPhen scores for the changes. The hands-on demonstrations and exercises first used the VEP web interface (this part is suitable for everybody), followed by VEP use via the standalone Perl script and REST API (this part was suitable for participants with coding experience).

Audience: This course was aimed at wet-lab researchers, clinicians and bioinformaticians who wanted to get hands-on experience using Ensembl to analyse variation data.

Learning outcomes

- Learn how to view variation data in the Ensembl browser
- Learn how to analyse your own variation data with the Variant Effect Predictor (VEP)

Variant analysis and prioritization (15 June 2016)

Session 1: [European Genome-phenome Archive](#) (Ilkka Lappalainen, CSC)

The European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA) is a permanent archive that promotes the distribution and sharing of genetic and phenotypic data consented for specific approved uses but not fully open, public distribution. The EGA follows strict protocols for information management, data storage, security and dissemination. Authorized access to the data is managed in partnership with the data-providing organizations. The EGA includes major reference data collections for human genetics research.

Session 2: [RD-Connect genomics analysis platform](#) (Sergi Beltran, Centro Nacional de Análisis Genómico)

The RD-Connect genomics analysis platform connects databases, registries, biobanks and clinical bioinformatics for rare disease research. The genomics side of the platform already includes hundreds of exomes linked to detailed phenotypes stored in PhenoTips using the Human Phenotype Ontology. Exomes have been processed with the RD-Connect standard analysis pipeline for genomics, which exceeds 99% precision and sensitivity when compared to the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) reference set of calls for NA12878. The exomes can be combined in a very flexible manner and variants can be filtered and prioritized through the user-friendly interface using the most common quality, genomic location, effect, pathogenicity and population frequency annotations, including CADD and

ExAC. In this session we learned what is the submission workflow to the RD-Connect platform and how one can access and analyse their data. The hands-on part allowed to try the genomics analysis platform.

Session 3: Variant prioritization with [UMD-Predictor](#), [VarAFT](#) and [Human Splicing Finder](#) (David Salgado, Aix Marseille Universite)

Sequencing generates huge amount of variants. Even after quality checks thousands of variants need to be prioritized to highlight potential causative mutations, often limited to one or two mutations depending on the mode of inheritance. This session covered the following systems which help with these tasks:

- UMD-Predictor, a pathogenicity prediction system for any human cDNA substitution leading to synonymous, missense or nonsense amino acid change.
- Human Splice Finder a pathogenicity prediction system for any intronic/exonic mutations that could impact splicing signals.
- VarAFT, a prioritization system to analyse and filter variations from NGS data.

During this training session, participants were introduced to these systems and used UMD-Predictor and VarAFT on real use-cases.

Session 4: Genome variant annotation and interpretation in a clinical context using [omnomicsNGS](#) (Christophe Roos, Eufomatics)

[omnomicsNGS](#) is a CE-marked software platform for clinical reporting on patient NGS data. It provides relevant genomic and mutation information for clinicians and molecular genetics laboratories based on patient data and external information sources. It can be tailored to report on markers in specific gene panels and it can also be used for analyses on rare genetic diseases using whole exome sequence data.

1.5. Next generation registries: going FAIR, going Gold

Rome, 27–29 July 2016

The main aim of this workshop was to align on next steps towards interoperable rare disease patient/disease registries between different representatives from the rare disease domain: patients, biobanks, registries, catalogues, software solution providers, and infrastructures (e.g. ELIXIR, BBMRI). The official report is due in September. Here, we summarize highlights. Consensus was reached on continued involvement with GA4GH and IRDIRC task forces on patient identifiers and practical computable ELSI, and task forces that address sustainability. Consensus was also reached (or confirmed) for the use of ontologies + Linked Data + FAIR data point APIs to implement the interoperability principle of the FAIR data principles for the rare disease domain. Four software solution providers agreed to collaborate on implementing support for FAIR principles in their tools based on recommendations from the rare disease community (which in turn works within ELIXIR to adopt FAIR principles).

The workshop was organised by partners in RD-Connect, particularly the Istituto Superiore di Sanità (<http://www.iss.it/>, Italy), with contributions from ELIXIR, a rare disease patient representative, RD-Connect and RaDiCo representatives for biobanks, registries and cohort studies, Orphanet, and software solution providers for patient/disease registries including PatientCrossroads (<https://www.patientcrossroads.com/>, USA), OSSE (<https://www.osse-register.de>,

Germany), RDRF (<https://muccg.github.io/rdrf/>, Australia), and the developers of ID-Cards, a registry of patient/disease registries and biobanks (<http://catalogue.rd-connect.eu/>, Austria).

The event was following the aim of delivering specific knowledge to the RD community to raise capacity of the participants.

2. Future events

A number of future training events are planned that will further enable establishment and more optimal maintenance of rare disease registries through specific f2f and e-learning courses with the help of WP11 and widespread and scaled up with the help of WP10.

2.1. RD-Connect and ELIXIR 4th International Summer School on RD and Orphan Drug Registries and RD-Connect BYOD Workshop to Link RD Registries⁵

26–30 September 2016

This event will be organised with the help of the External Relations Office, Istituto Superiore di Sanità. The event is open to health professionals, researchers, clinicians and representatives of patient associations engaged in rare disease patient registries. With the use of Problem-Based Learning methodology, where a problem serves as a didactic stimulus, the attendees will be introduced to the aims and needs of clinical research registries. The course covers: (i) resources needed to establish a clinical research registry; (ii) registry sustainability, including registry purposes, data and sharing, dissemination activities and the role of patient associations; (iii) the main steps for planning a registry and controlling its operation. The workshop consists of two parts:

- a. 4th International Summer School on Rare Disease and Orphan Drug Registries (26 – 28 September 2016) endorsed by ICORD (<http://icord.org/>). The training will use Problem-Based Learning. Scientific articles, expert lectures, consultations and feedback to support the attendees in solving the problem. <http://www.iss.it/cnmr/?lang=1&id=2662&tipo=3>
- b. RD-Connect BYOD Workshop to Link Rare Disease Registries (29 – 30 September 2016 in Rome) will be a hands-on experience, where the attendees work with FAIR data experts to make their (sample) data FAIR with a focus on interoperability, and link them to existing FAIR data. The event is co-organised by RD-Connect, ISS-CNMR, ELIXIR (<https://www.elixir-europe.org/>) and DTL(<http://www.dtls.nl/>), <http://www.iss.it/cnmr/?lang=1&id=2662&tipo=3>

⁵ <http://www.iss.it/cnmr/?lang=1&id=2662&tipo=3>

2.2. RD training needs survey

Until the end of 2016 the survey on RD training needs will be executed and analysed. There was a short delay in its execution, pending the WP11 general training needs survey to be finalised so that we can have the same and comparable core of questions. This will also allow us to make a reliable comparison of results between general training needs in life science information and RD community training needs. Based on the results of the survey a new course/workshop will be prepared in the first half of 2017 and where possible aligned with events in the rare disease domain throughout 2017. The courses/workshops will use e-learning and other training techniques successfully tested in the ELIXIR training platform within WP11 Train the Researcher (TtR) and Train the Trainer (TtT) subtasks. All course materials will also be available for RD-Connect.

2.3. Bring your own data workshops for registry software solution providers and molecular data

Based on earlier assessments of requirements and gaps in the rare disease domain, two BYODs are in preparation. A BYOD for patient registry software solution providers addresses the issue that patient and disease registries are typically developed by third party software developers for rare disease specialists. Having support for FAIR data built into the software will increase the interoperability of the resulting registries. The second BYOD addresses the goal to enable linking data at the level of phenotypes to data at the level of molecular processes. Each BYOD is treated as part of an implementation study and is coordinated via the overarching, cross-project data linkage plan through which also the specific rare disease areas and use cases are defined.

3. References

- Slides RD-CONNECT WORKSHOP 24 - 25 September 2015
<http://www.iss.it/binary/cnmr4/cont/Slide1.zip>
- 3rd International SummerSchool 2015 speakers slide presentations
http://www.iss.it/binary/cnmr4/cont/3rd_International_SummerSchool_2015_speakers_slide_presentations.zip
- Data linkage and tutorial RD-CONNECT WORKSHOP 24 - 25 September 2015
http://www.iss.it/binary/cnmr4/cont/RD_Connect_workshop_data_linkage_and_Tutorial.zip